

Supplementary data

Enhanced olfactory performance in deaf Dalmatians: evidence for neurosensory compensation?

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Online Resource S1. Experimental setup: kibble composition and volatile profile, hiding spot classification, training session design, and layout of the search environment

a. Kibble composition

Elements	Tapioca, wheat gluten, wheat flour, vegetable fibers, hydrolyzed animal proteins, mineral salts
Analytical constituents	Crude protein: 20% – Crude fat: 1% – Crude ash: 2.3% – Crude fiber: 1.9% – Moisture: 15%

Source: https://www.royalcanin.com/fr/dogs/products/retail-products/educ-3100?srsId=AfmBOorGcrrigG8URqE_9QTC9f0bProJarYj1CYIp9hXysRhco3Kb8Kq

b. Kibble volatile profiles

Volatile profiles were analyzed via gas chromatography–mass spectrometry following solid-phase microextraction triple-phase divinylbenzene/carboxen/polydimethylsiloxane (DVB/CAR/PDMS). The volatile compounds were separated using an Agilent 7890A GC (Hewlett-Packard, Palo Alto, Santa Clara, USA) equipped with a fused-silica capillary DB-Wax column (30 m × 0.25 mm id., 0.5-µm film thickness) (Agilent J & W, Santa Clara, USA) and were identified using a 5975C mass selective detector (MSD) (Agilent J & W, Santa Clara, USA).

Chromatograms were overlaid across five kibbles from the same bag and two kibbles from three distinct bags representing different production batches. Compound identification was performed on the 22 most intense peaks of the chromatograms, and peak areas were compared to assess the variability of each sample. Analyses were performed by the Chemosens Laboratory (INRAE, Dijon, France).

c. Classification of hiding spot types

Five distinct hiding spot types were defined based on their location, visibility, and elevation:

- **Type 1:** On the floor, visible, located <2 meters from the room entrance
- **Type 2:** On the floor, visible, located >2 meters from the entrance
- **Type 3:** Elevated, visible
- **Type 4:** On the floor, hidden (kibble not visible)
- **Type 5:** Elevated, hidden (kibble not visible)

Kibbles were never placed in exactly the same location across trials. However, each trial used a hiding spot consistent with the characteristics defined above to maintain standardization.

d. Training session structure

The learning phase consisted of five distinct training session types (A to E), each comprising five trials with pre-assigned hiding spot types:

- **Session A:** Type 1, Type 1, Type 2, Type 2, Type 1
- **Session B:** Type 1, Type 2, Type 3, Type 3, Type 1
- **Session C:** Type 2, Type 3, Type 4, Type 4, Type 1
- **Session D:** Type 3, Type 4, Type 5, Type 5, Type 1
- **Session E:** One hiding spot of each type (Types 1 to 5)

Progression through these sessions was required for all dogs before entering the evaluation phase.

e. Search environment layout

The search task was conducted in a controlled indoor environment—the institutional physiology library. A schematic layout of the room is provided below. After each trial, the hiding areas were wiped with a damp cloth to remove scent traces. The room was ventilated thoroughly between sessions to minimize olfactory cues from previous trials.

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<https://www.chemosens.com/>

platform (INRAE, Dijon,
of food products (see:

a. Intra-bag variability

Chromatographic profiles of five individual kibbles from the same bag were obtained using solid-phase microextraction followed by gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (SPME-GC-MS). The x-axis represents retention time (in minutes), and the y-axis indicates signal intensity. After overlaying, results show highly consistent chromatograms, indicating a stable volatile compound composition across kibbles from a single bag (Chemosens, 2023).

Identification of the 22 most intense volatile organic compounds in six kibble samples from three different bags and two distinct production batches (A14/B14, A23/B23, and A25/B25) (Chemosens, 2024).

No.	RT (min)	Compound	CAS	Exp. RI	Lit. RI	CV (%)
1	2.76	Acetone	67-64-1	800	802	13.5
2	3.37	2-Methylfuran	534-22-5	860	856	19.6
3	3.75	Methanol	67-66-1	891	892	7.8
4	3.79	Butan-2-one	78-93-3	893	894	10.7
5	3.99	2-Methylbutanal	96-17-3	908	906	19.6
6	4.06	3-Methylbutanal	590-86-3	911	913	19.1

7	4.39	Ethanol	64-17-5	933	934	8.8
8	7.75	Hexanal	66-25-1	1094	1094	15.4
9	9.10	Pent-3-en-2-one	625-33-2	1138	1138	11.1
10	10.13	Pent-1-en-3-ol	616-25-1	1171	1174	8.9
11	10.83	5-Methylhexan-2-one	110-12-3	1193	1188	15.4
12	10.96	Dodecane	112-40-3	1197	1200	4.7
13	11.68	3-Methylbutanol	123-51-3	1219	1218	7.1
14	12.39	2-Pentylfuran	377-69-3	1241	1244	16.7
15	13.09	Pentan-1-ol	71-41-0	1262	1260	4.7
16	15.58	2,5-Dimethylpyrazine	123-32-0	1338	1338	4.6
17	15.79	2,6-Dimethylpyrazine	108-50-9	1344	1344	4.9
18	16.48	Hexan-1-ol	111-27-3	1365	1362	6.1
19	19.58	Oct-1-en-3-ol	3391-86-4	1462	1458	6.6
20	19.70	Acetic acid	64-19-7	1465	1465	6.7
21	21.98	Benzaldehyde	100-52-7	1539	1537	7.6
22	25.36	Butanoic acid	107-92-6	1651	1647	13.3

RT (min): Retention time in minutes; CAS: Chemical Abstracts Service registry number; Exp. RI: Experimental retention index on a polar column (DB-Wax, Agilent); Lit. RI: Literature retention index on a polar column (DB-Wax); CV (%): Coefficient of variation across samples.

b. Comparison of kibbles from different bags and production batches

Chromatograms of three individual kibbles from different bags were obtained using SPME-GC-MS. The first chromatogram (top, black) corresponds to a kibble from a different production batch, while the second (middle, blue) and third (bottom, red) represent kibbles from two bags belonging to the same batch. While the overall volatile compound profiles were qualitatively similar across samples, some differences in the intensity of specific peaks were observed (Chemosens, 2024).

Abundance

Time-->
Abundance

Time-->
Abundance

Time-->

An overlay of the three chromatograms (black = A14, blue = A23, red = A25) highlights three compounds with coefficients of variation exceeding 20% across batches.

Identification of the 22 most intense volatile organic compounds in six kibble samples from three different bags and two distinct production batches (A14/B14, A23/B23, and A25/B25) (Chemosens, 2024).

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Online Resource S3. Dog Characteristics

Group	Sex and Neuter Status	Shoulder Height (cm)	Weight (kg)	Age (years)
Hearing	Neutered male	75	27	6
Hearing	Spayed female	67	23	6
Deaf	Neutered male	64	22	5
Deaf	Intact male	69	24	4

Online Resource S4. correlations between search speed, time since last meal, and time since previous session.

Variable	All dogs	Hearing group	Deaf group
Time since last meal	$r = -0.04$ [-0.26 ; 0.18]	$r = -0.01$ [-0.31 ; 0.30]	$r = 0.07$ [-0.24 ; 0.37]
	$p = 0.70$	$p = 0.96$	$p = 0.66$
Time since previous session	$r = 0.02$ [-0.20 ; 0.24]	$r = -0.003$ [-0.31 ; 0.31]	$r = -0.05$ [-0.36 ; 0.26]
	$p = 0.87$	$p = 0.98$	$p = 0.74$

Pearson correlation coefficients (r), 95% confidence intervals, and p -values are reported for the entire sample, as well as separately for the hearing and deaf groups. Variables considered include (1) the time elapsed since the dog's last meal and (2) the time elapsed since the previous session. These correlations aim to assess whether motivational or temporal factors influenced olfactory search speed.